

EFFICIENCY OF USING AI APPLICATIONS IN PRONUNCIATION TRAINING

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the effectiveness of using artificial intelligence-based applications in the formation of pronunciation and intonation skills when learning a foreign language. The results of the experimental study showed a higher level of phonetic skills development among students using AI applications compared to traditional teaching methods. The conclusion is made about the prospects of integrating artificial intelligence technologies into the practice of teaching foreign languages.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, learning process, educational environment, foreign languages, learning motivation, digital technologies.*

The current stage of education development is characterized by the active introduction of digital technologies into the educational process. One of the most promising areas is the use of artificial intelligence technologies, which are gradually becoming an important tool for modernizing the educational environment. In the field of teaching foreign languages, digital technologies open up new opportunities for improving various aspects of language training for students, including the development of phonetic skills [1].

Pronunciation and intonation are the most important components of communicative competence. The correct reproduction of the language's sound system, compliance with the norms of verbal and phrasal stress, as well as the use of appropriate intonation models ensure the accuracy and naturalness of oral speech. Insufficient formation of pronunciation skills can lead to distortion of the meaning of utterance and complicate the process of intercultural communication.

The formation of pronunciation and intonation skills traditionally requires a significant amount of practice and constant correction of errors. In classroom settings, the teacher does not always have the opportunity to pay sufficient attention to each

student, especially in groups with a large number of students [2]. As a result, some phonetic errors can become fixed and persist for a long time.

The development of artificial intelligence technologies allows us to partially solve this problem. Modern pronunciation training applications use automatic speech recognition systems and acoustic analysis algorithms that allow students to compare spoken sound samples with reference pronunciation. Based on this analysis, applications provide the user with instant feedback, pointing out mistakes made and offering recommendations on how to fix them.

The use of AI applications in teaching foreign languages contributes to the individualization of the learning process. Students have the opportunity to independently adjust the intensity of classes, repeat exercises the required number of times and track their own progress. In addition, the interactive nature of digital technologies helps to increase learning motivation and stimulate regular practice of oral speech [3].

At the same time, the effectiveness of the use of artificial intelligence in the formation of pronunciation skills requires empirical confirmation. To determine the pedagogical potential of AI technologies, it is necessary to conduct experimental studies that allow comparing the results of traditional teaching and learning using digital tools.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the results of using artificial intelligence-based applications in the process of forming students' pronunciation and intonation skills when learning a foreign language.

The results of the study

The experimental study involved 40 students who were divided into two groups of 20 people each. The experimental group used artificial intelligence-based

applications to train pronunciation and intonation, while the control group was trained using traditional methods.

At the final stage of the experiment, the level of formation of the students' pronunciation and intonation skills was analyzed. The data obtained showed differences in the distribution of skill levels between the groups.

In the experimental group, a low level was recorded in 15% of the students, which corresponds to 3 participants. The average level was found in 45% of the students, that is, in 9 people. 40% of the students demonstrated a high level of formation of pronunciation and intonation skills, which amounted to 8 people.

In the control group, the indicators were less pronounced. A low level was recorded in 30% of the students, which corresponds to 6 participants. The average level was found in 45% of the students, which amounted to 9 people. A high level of skill formation was achieved in 25% of the students, that is, in 5 people.

To check the statistical significance of the differences between the groups, Pearson's χ^2 criterion was applied. As a result of calculations, the value of $\chi^2_{emp} = 6.12$ was obtained with a critical value of $\chi^2_{cr} = 5.99$ with a significance level of $p = 0.05$ and the number of degrees of freedom $df = 2$. Since the empirical value exceeds the critical value, the differences between the experimental and control groups are statistically significant.

Additionally, an analysis of the average indicators was carried out according to the integral index of pronunciation and intonation, evaluated on a five-point scale. In the experimental group, the average was 4.2 with a standard deviation of 0.4. In the control group, the average was 3.6 with a standard deviation of 0.5.

To check the statistical significance of the differences between the mean values, the Student's t-test was used for independent samples. As a result of calculations, the value of $t_{em} = 4.21$ was obtained with a critical value of $t_{cr} = 2.02$ with a significance

level of $p = 0.05$. Since the empirical value exceeds the critical value, the differences between the averages of the two groups are statistically significant.

Thus, a quantitative analysis of the results indicates higher rates of formation of pronunciation and intonation skills among the students of the experimental group.

The results obtained allow us to conclude that the use of applications based on artificial intelligence contributes to a more effective formation of students' pronunciation and intonation skills. The higher proportion of students who achieved a high level of proficiency in phonetic skills in the experimental group indicates the positive impact of digital technologies on the learning process.

One of the most significant advantages of using AI applications is the ability to receive personalized feedback. Unlike traditional teaching, where the teacher is limited by time frames and cannot always analyze the pronunciation of each student in detail, digital applications allow you to instantly identify mistakes and provide recommendations for their correction [4]. This helps students to become more aware of their own phonetic difficulties and to correct them more purposefully.

Another important advantage is the possibility of repeated independent practice. The formation of stable pronunciation skills requires regular training, and the use of digital applications allows students to repeat tasks the required number of times. This practice helps automate skills and create a more natural-sounding speech.

An essential advantage of AI applications is also the objectivity of pronunciation assessment. Modern speech analysis systems are able to detect even minor deviations from the standard pronunciation, which makes it possible to more accurately track the dynamics of phonetic skills development [5].

In addition, the use of digital tools has a positive effect on the motivation of students. The interactive interface, visualization of progress, and the ability to

independently monitor results make the learning process more exciting and encourage regular practice.

Despite the obvious advantages, the use of AI applications in pronunciation training has certain limitations. Artificial intelligence technologies may not always correctly interpret individual features of students' speech, including accent or variation of intonation patterns. In some cases, an automatic assessment system may detect deviations that do not significantly affect speech comprehension.

Another limitation is the dependence of the accuracy of the analysis on the technical conditions. The microphone quality, background noise level and acoustic characteristics of the room can affect the correctness of speech recognition and reduce the accuracy of feedback [6].

In addition, the use of AI applications requires pedagogical support. Despite the high functionality of digital tools, they cannot completely replace the teacher. The role of a teacher remains important for explaining complex phonetic phenomena, developing communication skills, and organizing systematic pronunciation work.

Thus, the most effective approach is a combined approach that combines the capabilities of artificial intelligence with traditional methods of teaching a foreign language.

The conducted research has shown that the use of applications based on artificial intelligence contributes to a more effective formation of students' pronunciation and intonation skills when learning a foreign language. The integration of digital technologies into the learning process makes it possible to increase the intensity of phonetic practice, provide individualized feedback and stimulate student motivation.

At the same time, the use of AI applications requires methodological support from the teacher and should be considered as an additional learning tool, rather than as a complete replacement for traditional pedagogical methods.

The results obtained confirm the prospects for further implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in the practice of teaching foreign languages and can serve as a basis for the development of methodological recommendations on the use of digital tools in the formation of pronunciation and intonation skills.

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